

POLITICAL SCIENCES

KAZAKHSTAN AND EURASIAN REGIONALISM: ROLE OF KAZAKHSTAN IN THE EURASIAN INTEGRATION PROCESS (PRACTICAL IMPLEMENTATION OF IDEAS)

Zhaksylyk A.

Al-Farabi Kazakh National University

Abstract

This article explores the role of Kazakhstan in regional cooperation within Eurasia and its influence on the process of Eurasian integration. The author analyzes the practical implementation of Kazakhstan's ideas to promote this process, including its participation in the Eurasian Economic Union and the Shanghai Cooperation Organization. The article highlights Kazakhstan's initiatives in trade, investment, infrastructure development, and cultural exchange, as well as its strategic role in ensuring stability and economic development in the region. The author concludes that Kazakhstan plays a key role in the realization of Eurasian integration and is ready to continue active participation in this process in the future.

Keywords: Kazakhstan, Eurasian regionalism, Eurasianism, integration process, regional cooperation, Eurasian Economic Union (EAEU), Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO), economic development, strategic partnership.

Following the dissolution of the USSR and the emergence of independent states, Kazakhstan has actively pursued long-term prospects for uniting former Soviet republics on novel grounds and in innovative formats. The nation consistently advocates for integration and occupies a central position in all integration endeavors within the post-Soviet sphere. It is Kazakhstan's foreign policy initiatives in Central Asia that enable it to assume a leading role as a regional actor in interstate relations within the region. In general, the Eurasian integration process is facilitated by the active foreign policy activities of the Republic of Kazakhstan in international organizations such as the CIS, the Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO), the Organization for Security and Co-operation in Europe (OSCE), the Collective Security Treaty Organization (CSTO), the Eurasian Economic Community (EurAsEC) in the past, and the Eurasian Economic Union (EAEU) currently, among others. Kazakhstan has always been at the forefront of creating economic unions in the post-Soviet space. The idea of Eurasian integration was first initiated by Nursultan Nazarbayev in 1994 [1]. In 1995, to foster closer and mutually beneficial economic cooperation, the Presidents of Belarus, Kazakhstan, and the Russian Federation signed the first agreement on the establishment of the Customs Union (later joined by Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan). In 2000, based on these agreements, the Eurasian Economic Community (EurAsEC) was established [2].

The creation of the Eurasian Customs Union was ensured through three separate agreements, in which Kazakhstan played an active role. The first agreement in 1995 guaranteed its establishment; the second in 1999 guaranteed its formation, while the third in 2007 declared the creation of a single customs territory and the formation of the Customs Union, which emerged as the Eurasian Customs Union or the Customs Union of Belarus, Kazakhstan, and Russia from January 1, 2010 [3].

The Eurasian Economic Community (EurAsEC), as an international economic organization of post-Soviet

countries, existed from 2001 to 2014. It was a complex process of economic cooperation, the formation, and functioning of the Customs Union and the Single Economic Space. This process was intricate, contradictory, and not always efficient. Therefore, having played its historically important, undoubtedly positive role, the community was abolished, and the Eurasian Economic Union (EAEU) was established as a closer integration association of countries. The idea of creating the EAEU belongs to Nursultan Nazarbayev (he even proposed a single currency - "altyn" as early as 2012). The idea of a currency was not supported, but the creation of a more efficiently functioning economic union was not only supported by Vladimir Putin, Dmitry Medvedev, Alexander Lukashenko, but also implemented [4].

The Eurasian Economic Union (EAEU) is an international economic integration union, the treaty for the creation of which was signed on May 29, 2014, and came into force on January 1, 2015 [5]. The EAEU is designed to ensure the free movement of goods, services, capital, and labor resources, as well as to implement joint infrastructure and investment projects. Based on universal integration principles, the EAEU has the potential to play an important role in harmonizing processes in the European and Eurasian regions. In strategic terms, for Nursultan Nazarbayev, the EAEU should have:

- become a competitive global economic union;
- served as a solid link connecting the developing Euro-Atlantic and Asian regions, and become part of a new global monetary-financial system;
- underwent geo-economic and, in the future, geopolitical development of Eurasian integration through evolutionary and voluntary processes;
- developed only with broad societal support.

From the outset, the Eurasian Economic Union (EAEU) didn't not pose obstacles to Kazakhstan's multi-vector, multi-polar foreign policy, nor did it hinder Kazakhstan's participation in other regional associations that align with the country's priorities and goals. The EAEU represents a completely new type of inte-

gration among post-Soviet states, based on the inviolability of legislation and excluding any pressure or dominance. In his speech at the meeting of the Supreme Eurasian Economic Council on May 29, 2013, Nursultan Nazarbayev outlined the fundamental principles of Eurasian integration: further work within the framework of Eurasian integration will be based on the principles of mutual benefit, equality, evolution, pragmatism, practicality, and the inviolability of political sovereignty [6].

What was the Eurasian economic integration supposed to bring to the Republic of Kazakhstan? Firstly, Kazakhstan was expected to gain stronger negotiation positions and competitive advantages in economic relations with third countries. Kazakh producers, by gaining access to Russian transport infrastructure, began to reduce their export costs, thereby increasing the competitiveness of their products in European markets. Secondly, an important economic prerequisite for the development of Eurasian integration was the task of overcoming the raw material dependency of the Kazakh economy, which would accelerate the country's industrialization. Thirdly, reaching a new level of economic integration, conducting a unified foreign trade policy with union countries, forming a common space for technical regulation, and improving the coordination of the development of key sectors of the country's economy were crucial. Fourthly, a single market with Russia, Belarus, and other union countries would also allow Kazakhstan to become a bridge between the powerful economies of China and the European Union.

Since May 6, 2017, a single market for medicinal products and medical devices has been operating in the EAEU member states [7]. Within the EAEU, agreements have been reached to form a common market for oil and oil products by 2025 [8]. It envisages the non-application of export customs duties and restrictions in mutual trade. Additionally, by 2025, access to gas transportation infrastructure will be provided. Kazakhstan is interested in resolving these issues. The member states of the EAEU have interconnected systems for the supply of oil and oil products. Applying common trade conditions without barriers will ensure stability and balance in the operation of these systems. In the context of slowing global economic growth rates, Kazakhstan's participation in Eurasian economic integration creates the necessary foundation for economic diversification and increased labor productivity.

Currently, more than 25 memorandums of cooperation and interaction have been signed between the EAEU and various countries, including Mongolia, Chile, Peru, Singapore, and Cambodia [8]. On October 5, 2016, the Free Trade Agreement with Vietnam entered into force, which is the first preferential agreement within the EAEU [9]. Free trade agreements have been signed with Iran, Singapore, and Serbia. On October 25, 2019, the Agreement on Trade and Economic Cooperation between the EAEU and China entered into force (signed on May 17, 2018) [10]. In November 2020, the Agreement on the Exchange of Information on Goods and Vehicles of International Transport Moved Across the Customs Borders of the EAEU and China came into force from June 6, 2019. Efforts are

underway to identify points of convergence with the European Union and the Shanghai Cooperation Organization. The course is set for alignment between the EAEU and the Chinese initiative "Belt and Road."

Despite external negative factors, by the end of 2022, the economy of Kazakhstan achieved a confident GDP growth rate of 3.1%, reaching \$225.2 billion. Kazakhstan's mutual trade with the EAEU countries increased by 7.1% compared to 2021 (from January to November 2021 - \$23.9 billion, from January to November 2022 - \$25.6 billion). Kazakhstan's exports to the EAEU for the 11 months of 2022 increased by 22.3% (from January to November 2021 - \$7.1 billion, from January to November 2022 - \$8.6 billion). Kazakhstan's imports from the EAEU countries increased by 0.7% (from January to November 2021 - \$16.8 billion, from January to November 2022 - \$17 billion) [11]. It is worth noting that Kazakhstan's mutual trade with partners during the operation of the EAEU has increased by 60%. The share of trade with the EAEU in Kazakhstan's total trade as of the end of 2021 amounted to 25.7%. Meanwhile, Kazakhstan's exports to the EAEU during the Union's operation period increased by 34.9%. At the same time, the gross inflow of foreign direct investment into Kazakhstan from EAEU countries by the end of 2021 exceeded the investment volume of 2015 by 3.2 times (2015 - \$0.6 billion, 2021 - \$1.97 billion). Investments from third countries increased by 46.6% and amounted to \$21.7 billion in 2021 (in 2015 - \$14.8 billion), which is also a result of Kazakhstan being part of the common EAEU market [12].

The number of joint ventures with EAEU countries in Kazakhstan has increased by 2.4 times from 2015 to January 2022, reaching 14,894 [13]. They operate in various sectors including industry, construction, trade, services, and others. As for the decisions that have come into force within the EAEU, on October 27, 2022, regulations governing the circulation of veterinary diagnostic products within the customs territory of the EAEU were approved. These regulations establish unified procedures for assessing the quality of veterinary diagnostic products, a single registration procedure, and information exchange among the authorized bodies of the EAEU member states during the implementation of state control (supervision) over their circulation.

In 2022, the Union bodies held 70 meetings (the Supreme Eurasian Economic Council, the Intergovernmental Council, the Council, and the Collegium of the EEC), during which 415 decisions, 328 directives, 73 instructions, and 51 recommendations were adopted. Within the framework of the Supreme Eurasian Economic Council and the Eurasian Intergovernmental Council, Kazakhstan voiced 131 initiatives, which is the highest indicator among all EAEU members [14]. For comparison, the Republic of Belarus, which comes in second place, voiced 95 initiatives. It is worth noting that Kazakhstan's initiatives are the most relevant and in demand. Currently, 9 initiatives are in the process of implementation, while the remaining 122 initiatives have already been fulfilled. Kazakhstan's initiatives cover various areas of practical cooperation: industrial

cooperation, digitization of economies, public procurement, etc.

Moreover, within the EAEU, an integrated information system (IIS) is actively developing, aimed at facilitating interstate data exchange and electronic document exchange within the Union, creating common information resources for EAEU member states, implementing common processes, and ensuring the functioning of EAEU bodies. It is no secret that timely and high-quality information exchange will help address a significant portion of the issues arising from the movement of goods within the EAEU in the areas of veterinary, sanitary, phytosanitary, transport, and customs control. These issues are particularly important under current conditions.

On December 9, 2022, at the summit of the heads of state of the EAEU member states, the Key Directions of International Cooperation for 2023 were approved [15]. The priority directions for 2023 included the development of systematic dialogue with the Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO), ASEAN, BRICS countries, interaction with international organizations (UNCTAD, WIPO, WCO, WTO, ICAT, etc.), and third countries (Argentina, Bangladesh, Hungary, Greece, Indonesia, Cambodia, South Korea, Mongolia, UAE, etc.). As of today, the EEC has concluded 46 memoranda with international organizations, 14 with regional integration and interstate associations, and 27 with third countries. In general, against the backdrop of the evolving geopolitical situation, Kazakhstan's position on Eurasian integration is of strategic relevance. It is noteworthy that in 2024, the Republic of Kazakhstan will chair the Eurasian Economic Commission (EEC), an organization that plays a pivotal role in shaping both the format and the macroeconomic model across the Eurasian continent.

The format of the EAEU helps maintain positive dynamics in the development and support of integration ties, which is reflected in direct investments for Kazakhstan. In December 2023, the Russian Ambassador to Kazakhstan announced official figures on this direction: "In 2023, the trade volumes between the two countries continued to grow and reached a record level of 1.8 trillion rubles. From January to September 2023, the volumes of mutual trade increased by 17% compared to the same period [16]." According to him, the share of settlements in national currencies is also increasing, reaching 75%. In turn, the Republic of Kazakhstan is rapidly increasing its exports to Russia. In the first half of 2023, this indicator exceeded \$1.3 billion USD (according to the National Statistics Bureau of the Agency for Strategic Planning and Reforms of Kazakhstan). Among the goods exported by Kazakhstan to Russia are machinery and equipment, products of the chemical industry, metals and metal products. Meanwhile, Kazakhstan's imports from Russia mainly consist of food products, mineral products, chemical industry products, and timber.

Additionally, one of the priorities for the development of the Kazakhstani economy has always been the transportation and logistics sector, and against the backdrop of global trade changes, its role has increased even more. Strengthening cooperation with the EAEU

can help Kazakhstan become a major transportation and logistics hub along the North-South and East-West corridors. To achieve this, the Republic of Kazakhstan is already modernizing border checkpoints at the external borders of the EAEU and plans to build trade and logistics centers along the Caspian Sea coast by 2026.

In the report "Regional Economic Prospects" by the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (EBRD), analysts of this financial institution were surprised to note that contrary to forecasts, Kazakhstan's economic growth in the reporting period of 2022 reached 3.4%, instead of the previously mentioned 2% [17]. The reason for Kazakhstan's economic growth was not only the export of oil but also the influx of new clients from Russia and Belarus into the banking sector of Kazakhstan. Another component of the unexpected success of the Kazakh economy in 2022, from a Western perspective, was the increase in income due to the re-export of computers, household appliances and electronics, auto parts, electrical and electronic components to Russia. Thanks to the EAEU, Kazakhstan benefits from anti-Russian sanctions, primarily through the growth of non-raw material exports, which is critically important for the country's trade diversification.

At the II Eurasian Economic Forum "Eurasian Integration in a Multipolar World" held in Moscow in 2023, the President of Kazakhstan, Kassym-Jomart Tokayev, delivered a speech. Essentially, the President of Kazakhstan outlined a fundamentally new vision for the balance of power on the Eurasian continent, reflecting the changed matrix of relations between states both within the EAEU and along its perimeter. This vision reflects a new reality, which became even more apparent after the "Central Asia-China" summit held in Xi'an a week earlier, reaffirming the trends in the implementation of the "One Belt, One Road" project initiated by Chinese President Xi Jinping a decade ago. Now, EAEU members will have to adjust their plans and projects to these trends. Tokayev emphasized the special role of Kazakhstan in this large-scale process, as he had already mentioned in an interview with Chinese television. In his opinion, Kazakhstan can become the center of the entire Eurasian region, and the leadership of Kazakhstan will strive to strengthen this position. However, Tokayev also pointed out the dissonance in the work of the EAEU, referring to the increasingly active military-political rapprochement between Russia and Belarus, even making a joke about shared nuclear weapons. However, such rapprochement became possible due to the presence of common Slavic roots and is not suitable for all EAEU members. The President of Kazakhstan noted that there are now two levels of integration: one within the Russian-Belarusian union with the highest level of military and political coordination, and the other with the other EAEU members - Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, and Armenia [18]. As for the Central Asian states specifically, which are part of the EAEU, they will have to integrate primarily within their own region, but with full coordination of actions and financial support from China. At the same time, Russia will remain an important economic partner for Kazakhstan, which has no access to the sea (excluding the Caspian

Sea). Kazakhstan intends to use Russia's transit territory and assistance in implementing major infrastructure projects.

On July 4, 2023, the Republic of Kazakhstan assumed the chairmanship of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO) for the fourth time, making it the most influential international organization in continental Asia today. Assessing the role of the SCO in the modern world, President of Kazakhstan K.K. Tokayev stated at the SCO summit in Delhi in July of that year: "I am confident that with significant political influence, substantial economic opportunities, and colossal human resources, the SCO is capable of making a significant contribution to achieving the goals of sustainable development and overcoming the contemporary challenges facing humanity [19]". He has defined six main priorities for its chairmanship in the organization:

- 1) Ensuring security and stability within the SCO space;
- 2) Expanding trade and economic ties;
- 3) Strengthening energy cooperation;
- 4) Expanding cooperation in the digital sphere;
- 5) Strengthening cooperation in the field of ecology;
- 6) Developing cultural and humanitarian ties.

The format for their implementation includes a comprehensive set of activities that will be carried out jointly with other member states throughout 2023-2024. Additionally, the traditional task of the SCO remains in focus during the chairmanship – combating the "three forces of evil" and transnational crime. In this context, Kazakhstan's proposals include the update of the Cooperation Program to Counter Terrorism, Separatism, and Extremism for 2025-2027, the adoption of the SCO Anti-Drug Strategy for 2024-2029, and the Action Program for its implementation [20].

To expand trade and economic ties within the SCO, Kazakhstan proposes focusing on creating favorable conditions to increase mutual trade turnover, removing existing trade barriers, and launching joint ventures. According to President K.K. Tokayev, to enhance the organization's investment attractiveness, it is expedient to begin creating a "SCO Economic Preferences" base and to utilize the potential of the Astana International Financial Center to stimulate direct and portfolio investments in regional SCO projects. A significant breakthrough in developing the investment potential of the SCO could be Kazakhstan's proposed idea of establishing an SCO Investment Fund. In a joint communiqué adopted at the meeting of the Council of Heads of Government of SCO member states in Bishkek on October 26, 2023, this initiative was noted by participants as worth of consideration [21].

Kazakhstan will pay significant attention to the development of transport connectivity, both intra-regional and transcontinental, which can give a powerful boost to expanding trade and economic ties in Eurasia. Astana intends to engage stakeholders in linking the Chinese Belt and Road Initiative with the Trans-Caspian International Transport Route and implementing regional infrastructure projects within the SCO area. As a practical measure, Kazakhstan has proposed creating a Partnership Network of major strategic ports and logistics

centers. Our country hopes that at the Astana Summit of the organization in 2024, member states will coordinate and adopt the SCO Energy Strategy. A crucial feature of modern global development is also the rapid integration of digital technologies into all spheres of life, forming the basis of the economy of the future. Therefore, Kazakhstan aims to expand cooperation among SCO countries in the digital sphere – both to systematically reduce digital inequality between different countries and social groups and to ensure favorable conditions for their sustainable economic development. In this regard, Kazakhstan offers its services as a Digital Hub within the SCO. The practical implementation of this priority of Kazakhstan's chairmanship will be facilitated by the organization of the SCO Digital Forum in Astana in 2024, which is planned to be combined with the first meeting of the Management Commission of the Pool of Technoparks and Innovation Clusters [22].

A traditional element of today's political culture in international relations is the development of cultural and humanitarian ties. As part of this priority, Kazakhstan has proposed declaring the city of Almaty as the tourist and cultural capital of the SCO during its chairmanship. Additionally, to promote shared ideals and values of the "Shanghai Spirit" worldwide, the launch of the "SCO Spiritual Shrines" project is envisaged. Kazakhstan also suggests hosting the "Golden Horde and Its Legacy" conference in Turkistan in 2024, during which the mausoleum of Khoja Ahmed Yasawi – a prominent thinker and religious figure of the medieval East – will be presented. In a broader sense, Kazakhstan advocates for updating the SCO with its vision of global development, strengthening the organization's potential in new geopolitical conditions, and further institutionalizing it. In this regard, Kazakhstan has proposed the adoption of a new SCO Development Strategy, a Concept for Strengthening the SCO's Potential, and the establishment of a Council of Permanent Representatives to the SCO, granting them the authority of full representation of the interests of member states. Thus, as President K.K. Tokayev concluded his speech at the SCO Summit in Delhi in July of last year, "Taking over the chairmanship, we will continue with all member states, regardless of their status in the organization, active and fruitful work for the benefit of further strengthening security, peace, and prosperity within the SCO".

So as we can see, at present, the primary focus of Eurasian integration lies in the economic sphere rather than the political one. The establishment of the Eurasian Economic Union marks the culmination of years of efforts and aspirations for integration, comprising Kazakhstan, Russia, Belarus, Armenia, and Kyrgyzstan. This union primarily serves economic purposes, mirroring the historical trajectory of European integration, which initially centered around economic objectives. Similar to the European Union's model, successful integration in Eurasia requires a driving force, with Kazakhstan, Russia, and Belarus assuming this role in the Eurasian context.

In summary, Kazakhstan holds a pivotal position in Eurasian regionalism and the integration process across the Eurasian landscape. Its active involvement in bodies like the Eurasian Economic Union (EAEU) and

the Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO) underscores its dedication to fostering economic collaboration, regional stability, and cohesion among Eurasian nations. Kazakhstan's commitment to advancing Eurasian regionalism is evident through various initiatives aimed at enhancing trade, investment, infrastructure, and cultural exchange throughout the region. Leveraging its strategic location, robust infrastructure networks, and abundant resources, Kazakhstan emerges as a key actor in Eurasian integration endeavors. Moreover, Kazakhstan's diplomatic endeavors and engagement with neighboring states highlight its role as a conduit between Europe and Asia, facilitating dialogue and cooperation on diverse fronts, including trade, transportation, security, and environmental sustainability. Looking ahead, Kazakhstan is poised to continue actively promoting Eurasian integration, leveraging its strengths and nurturing closer relationships with regional partners. By capitalizing on past achievements and embracing new opportunities for collaboration, Kazakhstan can significantly contribute to the realization of a more integrated and prosperous Eurasian community.

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